

Cyanoethylation of 1,2,4-Triazolin-5-Ones

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Cyanoethylation of 4-aryl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones, as a class of compounds, has not been so far studied, although cyanomethylation of the system has been well studied¹.

As an extension to our studies² on cyanoethylation of heterocyclic compounds, this investigation was taken up. The required 4-aryl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones were prepared by known methods^{3,4} starting from the corresponding 4-arylsenicarbazides. Cyanoethylation of the 1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones with acrylonitrile in ethanol in presence of sodium methoxide proceeded smoothly to give 1-cyanoethyl derivatives in 40–60% yields. The I.R. data (carbonyl band at 1720 cm⁻¹ and cyano band at 2225 cm⁻¹) showed that cyanoethylation had proceeded on nitrogen. This observation is in conformity with the reported¹ information that cyanomethylation takes place on nitrogen. All the 1-cyanoethyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones synthesised in this context are listed in Table 1.

TABLE I

Analytical data of 1-cyanoethyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones

No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C*	Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1	H	Phenyl	94–95	26.43	26.17
2	Methyl	Phenyl	103–04	24.78	24.57
3	Ethyl	Phenyl	59–60	23.20	23.14
4	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	97–98	24.66	24.57
5	H	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	100–01	22.71	22.93
6	Methyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	98–99	21.68	21.71
7	Ethyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	109–10	20.34	20.59
8	H	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	81–82	22.69	22.53
9	Methyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	107	21.56	21.33
10	Ethyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	93–94	20.12	20.25
11	H	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	93	22.36	22.53
12	Methyl	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	111–12	21.25	21.33

* All melting-points are uncorrected.

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EXPERIMENTAL

1-Cyanoethyl-4-phenyl-1, 2, 4-triazolin-5-one : 4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-one (3.2 g.; 0.02 mole) and acrylonitrile (2.7 g.; 0.05 mole) were refluxed in ethanol (100 ml.) containing sodium methoxide (0.2 g.) for 2 hrs. Alcohol was distilled off *in vacuo*. The residue was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (1*N*; 25 ml.) and then extracted with benzene (30 × 2 ml.). The benzene phase was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate, concentrated to 10 ml. and diluted with hexane to obtain the crude title product. It was crystallised from benzene-hexane; m.p. 94–95°; 2.5 g.

The rest of the 1-cyanoethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones were similarly prepared.

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